

Secondary Use of Health Data for Training Generative AI Models: Risks and Interplay between the EHDS and the AI Act

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Chatbots and virtual assistants powered by generative artificial intelligence (AI) are rapidly being integrated into healthcare settings, where they respond to patient queries, provide information, and support care pathways through personalised interactions. Recent evidence suggests that patients may perceive such systems as more empathetic and higher in quality than human clinicians,² while major technology providers have begun actively promoting consumer-facing generative AI tools tailored to health contexts.³ These developments intensify reliance on systems that are trained, tested and refined using large volumes of health data. This contribution examines the tension between, on the one hand, the need for high-quality, representative health datasets to ensure accuracy, mitigate bias⁴ and reduce the risk of hallucinations⁵ and clinically harmful outputs⁶ in generative AI systems, and, on the other hand, privacy risks associated with the secondary use of health data for AI training. Particular attention is paid to risks of model memorisation,⁷ which raise concerns in patient-facing applications, as models can, under certain conditions, memorise and reproduce fragments of its training data, creating the possibility that health information could be inadvertently revealed. Against this backdrop, the contribution analyses the emerging EU regulatory framework, focusing on the interplay between the European Health Data Space (EHDS) and the Artificial Intelligence Act (AI Act). It explores how the EHDS framework for secondary use of health data - explicitly permitting the training, testing and evaluation of algorithms under controlled conditions - interacts with the AI Act's requirements for general-purpose and high-risk systems, including obligations relating to data governance, quality, accuracy and risk management. Finally, it considers how proposed changes in data rules under the Digital Omnibus, specifically by creating an additional exemption for processing residual sensitive data in AI training datasets, will fit into the existing framework and possibly undermine the protection of data subjects.

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² Ayers J.W., A. Poliak, M. Dredze, et al. Comparing Physician and Artificial Intelligence Chatbot Responses to Patient Questions Posted to a Public Social Media Forum. *JAMA Intern Med.* 2023, 183(6): 589-596. doi:10.1001/jamainternmed.2023.1838

³ OpenAI. *Introducing ChatGPT Health: A dedicated experience in ChatGPT designed for health and wellness*, 7 Jan. 2026. Available at: <https://openai.com/index/introducing-chatgpt-health/>, last accessed on 27 Jan. 2026; Anthropic. *Advancing Claude in healthcare and the life sciences*, 11 Jan. 2026. Available at: <https://www.anthropic.com/news/healthcare-life-sciences>, last accessed on 27 Jan. 2026.

⁴ Omiye J.A., H. Gui, S.J. Rezaei, et al. Large language models in medicine: The potentials and pitfalls: A narrative review. *Annals of Internal Medicine*, 2024, 177(2): 210-220. <https://doi.org/10.7326/M23-2772>

⁵ Walters W.H., and E.I. Wilder. Fabrication and errors in the bibliographic citations generated by ChatGPT. *Scientific Reports*, 2023,13(1): 14045. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-41032-5>

⁶ Wu D., F. Haredasht, S. Maharaj, et al. First, do NOHARM: towards clinically safe large language models. arXiv:2512.01241v2 [cs.CY] 17 Dec. 2025. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2512.01241>

⁷ Xiong A., X. Zhao, A. Pappu, D. Song. The Landscape of Memorization in LLMs: Mechanisms, Measurement, and Mitigation. arXiv:2507.05578v2 [cs.LG] 12 Dec. 2025. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2507.05578>